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ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР АХБОРОТНОМАСИ

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USING OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS

ANNOTATION

The article describes ways to improve the quality of education of English teachers in general secondary schools through the use of innovative methods.

Keywords: school, innovation, pedagogue-technologist, method, education, upbringing, knowledge, skill, creative, classification, innovation, objective.

One of the critical elements of today is the use of the pedagogical innovations and successes that have been made. A teacher currently has access to a vast knowledge base of experiences that he can draw on throughout his career, and it is growing daily. However, it is difficult for teachers and future professionals to learn these experiences. The position of the teacher is especially important in creating best practices and popularizing them among colleagues. The educator should pay attention to the cost and effectiveness of the new advanced pedagogical practice.

The chance to apply the advancements produced as a consequence of theoretical pedagogical research into practice is provided by the teacher's practical activity being oriented toward innovation. It is vital to get these studies' findings known to the broader public in order to make them more widely accepted. Such news can be conveyed to representatives of other pedagogies by providing quick advice, conducting special seminars and trainings, giving speeches at conferences, and giving future pedagogues a series of lectures.

At this point, a question arises: "Who are the communicators and promoters of advanced pedagogical ideas and technologies to the general public?" Professors, teachers, and experienced educators employed by universities are crucial in researching and popularizing the experiences of a particular educator or educational institution. The reason for this can be explained as follows:

- the author of the innovation cannot give a necessary and accurate assessment of the perspective of a particular pedagogical idea or innovation;
- advanced pedagogues do not always think about popularizing their ideas. The reason is that innovation requires additional time and labor of the pedagogue;
- the idea is not always scientifically and methodologically justified by its creator; - the authors face obstacles related to the individual characteristics of themselves and their colleagues when describing their innovations and ways of implementing them;
- the task of not only promoting and popularizing pedagogical innovations, but also making corrections to the quality of pedagogues based on them and enriching the professional knowledge and skills of future teachers is assigned to the creative group;
- the tasks of systematic selection of innovations, monitoring, evaluation of innovative ideas, technologies, enriching the work experience of higher educational institutions are also the responsibility of the members of the creative group.

The creative idea's creator abstains from managing tasks that have a practical application in mind. This kind of strategy establishes a foundation for developing an innovative educator's capabilities and guiding him toward a particular objective. In this approach, the abilities of the revolutionary pedagogy's creator and popularizer are concentrated in one place and focused on a certain objective. Innovative pedagogies have their own dimensions.

Pedagogical innovation consists of the following dimensions that shape the creative activity of the future teacher: how new the innovative methods are; its optimality; how effective; possibility of application in mass experiment and so on. The main measure of innovative methods is their novelty, results of scientific research and equality with advanced pedagogical experiences. For this reason, it's crucial for educators who want to participate in the creative process to comprehend what innovation actually entails.

For some teachers, the experiment might be brand-new, but not for others. Additionally, future educators may innovate the same strategy to a different degree. Given this, both aspiring educators and current educators should approach innovative and creative activities in accordance with their needs. According to the level of innovation, innovative methods that help to develop the creative functions of future pedagogues are manifested in several forms: absolute level; local-absolute degree; conditional degree; subjective level. The mass application of innovative pedagogical innovations is interpreted as a criterion for their evaluation.

This is mainly related to the technical support of the educational process and the uniqueness of the teacher's activity. The innovative use of pedagogical innovations in mass educational experiments shows up in the early stages of a teacher's job. Following testing and an unbiased evaluation, these technologies will be made available for usage by the general public. Future teachers' creative faculties should be developed utilizing cutting-edge techniques that are universally accepted and enable productive outcomes. Diagnostic methods aimed at studying the innovative activity of the teacher are also diverse. The use of diagnostic methods shows the strengths of the teacher's activity. Therefore, equipping future teachers with modern methods of diagnosis is the demand of the times. Taking into account the professional needs and desires of future teachers, it is necessary to form professional and pedagogical ethics in them, and implement full-fledged purposeful activities aimed at continuous development.

It's important to remember that each pedagogue's experience includes both positive, developing circumstances and bad expressions while examining pedagogical innovations based on diagnosis. A young pedagogue must be able to clearly demonstrate both the positive and bad parts of his job experience on the basis of diagnosis in order to function well in an educational setting. It should be clearly conveyed to future teachers that the diagnostic methods used for the purpose of studying innovative processes are as follows:

- systematic study of pedagogical needs, interests, directions of special importance of future teachers, identifying difficulties encountered in teachers' work and opportunities to overcome them;
- search for ideas, concepts and advanced pedagogical experiences that serve to satisfy their interests and needs and introduce them into the practice of higher pedagogical education;
- to determine the originality of future teachers in the process of mastering and applying pedagogical innovations and their various manifestations, in which to demonstrate, describe, hold open classes, work on new resources, such as organizing lectures, participation in experimental work, and wide use of types of work. It is advised to carry out practical activity aimed at learning in stages based on the diagnosis of pedagogical innovations. Initial steps include asking prospective teachers to fill out questionnaires, reviewing their responses, setting up one-on-one interviews to corroborate the details in their questionnaire responses, and analyzing the information gleaned based on the findings of the diagnostic.

At this stage, based on the results of the first stage, activities aimed at improving the professional and pedagogical qualifications of the future teacher will be planned and the ways of their implementation will be shown.

At this point, the work has been finished, and additional diagnostic testing has been done. The goal of this approach is to deliver interim and final outcomes to the future instructor. Students' changes in group engagement are carefully examined. In order to effectively develop students' creative activities, it will be necessary to diagnose the professional skills, backgrounds, and experiences of future teachers, equip them with diagnostic techniques, and restructure the professional pedagogical education process based on cutting-edge concepts. As a result, there is an opportunity to encourage future teachers to be creative and take initiative. The creative pedagogical activity of the teacher is the process of positively solving tasks subordinated to the formation of human consciousness and behavior, and most importantly, the creation of a generation of well-rounded people.

Additionally, the anticipated outcome is attained sooner and the desired educational aim is easily reached. This means that; - the teacher must be promoted to the level of a new professional position, such as "teacher-technologist," or "pedagogue-technologist;" - "teacher-technologist" must have specialized knowledge, skills, and qualifications; - it is necessary to take specific measures to ensure the prestige, potential increase, spiritual and material interests of the "teach" In order to improve the quality of education, the use of innovative technologies by teachers in the course of the lesson will certainly give effective results.

In conclusion, our pedagogic teachers nowadays use cutting-edge and creative pedagogical technology in order to train mature experts who have a high degree of general professional culture, social engagement, independent thinking, and the ability to complete their work without difficulty. They should be aware that it is the primary factor raising the standard and effectiveness of education and that it is necessary given the demands of the modern world.

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